

STRAIN RATE AND TEMPERATURE EFFECTS ON THE DAMAGE AND STRENGTH OF GLASS/EPOXY CROSSPLY LAMINATES

Jean-Luc LATAILLADE, Marc DELAET, *Christian WOLFF, Francis COLLOMBET
Laboratoire Matériaux Endommagement Fiabilité
Ecole Nationale Supérieure d'Arts et Métiers, Bordeaux, France
* RENAULT S. A., Rueil-Malmaison, France

ABSTRACT

The specific absorption energy of structural elements based on composite materials is higher than those made of steel. However, this capacity may be limited due to some localized damage mechanisms, inducing a premature failure. Intralaminar cracking is one of such mechanisms and is investigated here in a broad range of strain rates using tensile specimens made of E Glass / Epoxy ($\pm\theta$)_s crossply laminates. Several interrupted dynamic tensile tests were performed thanks to modifications in a servo-hydraulic testing machine and in a Split Hopkinson tensile pressure bar. The damage caused by shear is investigated within the damage mechanics frame, permitting the access to the influence of the strain rate on damage threshold and damage propagation rate.

INTRODUCTION

For the safety of car users, vehicles have to be made with the aim to absorb, during a crash, great energy amounts resulting from deformation of the front of their structure. In this way, the passenger compartment can be protected from great deformations which could cause body damage. Some parts of a car are therefore adapted to the energy absorbing function which arises by solid deformation. Composite materials, intended for this energy absorbing function, get specific absorption capacities which are better than those of metallic materials [1]. However, energy absorption mechanisms of composite structures are quite different from metallic ones and are very complex [2]. As a general rule, two main crushing mechanisms are observed when cylindrical or rectangular tubes, for instance, are submitted to uniaxial compressive loading. A stable one allows large energy absorption capacities due to successive micro-cracks. However, a sudden and premature failure of the structure, without dissipated energy, often occurs due to the presence of an unstable brittle mechanism due to interlaminar shear, buckling or shear along fibres. Furthermore, cracking along fibres has been identified as a mechanism of great importance which is responsible for the unstable behaviour of such structures [2].

The aim of our study is therefore to characterise the intralaminar cracking damage process within long E glass reinforced epoxy composites which is due to shear stresses often coupled with some transverse stresses which has been chosen as tensile stresses, in order to get the most severe conditions. An approach by means of the damage mechanics is proposed. The mechanical tests are achieved by using several kinds of impact testing apparatus to investigate a large range of strain rates; these tests allow us to evaluate the high strain rate effects on the initiation and the propagation of the damage, assuming that the response of each sample is representative of the average material behaviour. A microscopic analysis allows us to localise and to identify the various damage initiation and propagation processes. Finally, a micromechanical calculation based on the stiffness prediction due to the MORI and TANAKA approach is proposed for predicting the macroscopic behaviour of composites by using a translation technique from the microscopic to the macroscopic scales.

UNIAXIAL TENSILE TEST ON $(\pm\theta)_S$ LAMINATES

$(\pm\theta)_S$ laminates are often tested under tension loading (Figure 1) since the fibre/matrix interphases play a great role within these particular structures. Furthermore, for an angle close to 45 degrees, intralaminar shear stresses get their maximal values with respect to transverse stresses [3].

Figure 1. Uniaxial tensile test on $(\pm\theta)_S$ crossply laminates.

It is worth noting that a small variation of the reinforcement angle has a considerable effect on the stress state change within each ply of the laminates. Three kinds of laminates are therefore used to investigate the influence of transverse stresses on the intralaminar shear behaviour of composite materials. The chosen samples are $(\pm 40)_S$, $(\pm 45)_S$ and $(\pm 50)_S$ laminates; the ratio of shear to transverse stresses decreases from 3.26 within (± 40) specimens to 1.67 within $(\pm 50)_S$ samples.

The longitudinal stresses within $(\pm\theta)_S$ laminates act on fibres. In this way, the behaviour of such structures is not influenced by these longitudinal stresses which are very lower than the fibre strength ($\sigma_R \approx 2500$ MPa).

The material under investigation is constituted with long E glass fibres embedded in an epoxy matrix. Fibre content is 43% by volume. 12 layers are manufactured from unidirectional prepreg with the required symmetrical stacking sequence. Thickness of these layers is (2.1 ± 0.1) mm. They are then machined with a water jet cutting system as dumbbell shape specimens. Special care is taken to avoid free edge delaminations. The effective length and width of each sample are respectively (15 ± 0.1) mm and (5.9 ± 0.1) mm. These sample sizes do not agree with any ASTM standard because none is defined where high strain rate tests are concerned. Indeed, the effective lengths of specimens must be short enough to induce within them a quasi-static loading state.

EXPERIMENTAL TECHNIQUES

The second step in developing the impact experimental program concerns the adaptation of several high strain rate testing devices from the previous uniaxial tensile test on $(\pm\theta)_S$ crossply laminates. To evaluate the damage evolution within samples, the tests are interrupted at various stresses or strains using the techniques described in this section.

First, to develop the study at medium strain rates (10 to 10^2 s^{-1}), an INSTRON high velocity servo-hydraulic testing machine is used within the range of 0.1 to 1 $m \cdot s^{-1}$ [4]. However, the principle of such an apparatus means that the hydraulic jack displacement cannot be stopped during the test. In this way, the sample under tension fails before the end of the test. To avoid this failure and to load samples up to different stress thresholds, a mechanical fuse has been designed [5]. It is held between the composite material and the hydraulic jack (Figure 2). The brittle failure of this fuse allows us to stop the test for chosen stress levels; the composite specimen is therefore damaged but not failed [4, 6].

At higher strain rate range (from 10^2 up to 10^3 s^{-1}), we use a modified tensile Split Hopkinson bar [4, 5, 6]. To damage samples at different stress thresholds [4, 5], interrupted tests are achieved by using different lengths for the projectiles which are propelled at the same velocity. Indeed, the duration of the wave created within the input bar, and hence the load duration, is proportional to these projectile lengths ($T = 2L/c$) in which T , L and c are respectively the wave duration, the projectile length and the wave velocity within it). However, the reflected waves at the free end of each bar have to be suppressed to avoid waves returning to the samples. For this purpose, the

reflected incident wave at the input bar/sample interface, as a compressive wave, is fully transmitted into the "trapping bar" previously located in contact with the free end of the input bar (Figure 3). The undesirable wave is therefore sufficiently trapped and the composite sample cannot be significantly loaded a second time. In a similar manner, the tensile wave within the output bar is transmitted into a tube which is able to slide along the bar (Figure 3). The new transmitted compressive wave allows the tube and the output bar to be separated and nearly no reflected wave reaches the specimen.

Figure 2. Schema of the servo-hydraulic testing machine with PMMA fuse.

Figure 3. Schematic representation of the Split Hopkinson tensile bars.

EXPERIMENTATION

Tensile tests on $(\pm\theta)_s$ crossply laminates to assess the damage mechanisms are achieved by means of the improved servo-hydraulic and Hopkinson pressure bars apparatus. Some loading curves for different stress thresholds are shown in Figure 4.

In order to investigate the microscopic damage processes which initiate the degradation of the $(\pm\theta)_s$ laminates in tensile loading, a damage analysis is made using an electron scanning micrography technique. A manual polishing of about (1.2 ± 0.2) mm in depth is achieved on one of the lateral sides (thickness section) of the damaged specimens. The microscopic analysis show that the degradation of each laminate is governed by the same process. First, the damage initiation occurs with some fibre-matrix interfaces unsticking (Figure 5.a). Then, this phenomenon grows around fibres (Figure 5.b) until the coalescence of the microcracks from one fibre to another. These microcracks propagate across the entire ply (Figure 5.c). No delamination is observed during the loading stage, except for $(\pm 50)_s$ specimens submitted to a high stress level. However, the damage kinetics are sensitive to the test conditions [4].

Figure 4 : Interrupted tensile tests on $(\pm 45)_S$ laminates by using : (a) the hydraulic set-up ($\dot{\epsilon} = 4.8 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and (b) the Hopkinson pressure bar apparatus ($\dot{\epsilon} = 265 \text{ s}^{-1}$).

Figure 5. Damage mechanism : (a) fibre-matrix debonding, (b) damage growth, (c) crack propagation.

To investigate, in a quantitative way, the strain rate and temperature effects on the damage processes, it is necessary to define some microscopic parameters which are representative of the damage level within the material. A model developed by PERREUX [8] allows us to define a microscopic damage indicator. This model consists in computing the mechanical properties of laminates which are damaged by some microcracks along fibres.

Damage being homogeneously distributed within specimens, the stiffness matrix of a damaged ply of the laminate is deduced, by using the effective stress concept, from the stiffness matrix of the undamaged ply and a damage tensor $\underline{D}^{L(i)}$ (Equation 2). The components of this damage tensor are deduced from an energetic approach and are proportional to the crack density within the considered ply. Then, the Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) allows us to compute the stiffness matrix of symmetric laminates as a function of the damaged ply stiffness matrix (Equation 3). Due

to the use of the CLT, this model is valid because no delamination is observed during the damage process of the $(\pm\theta)_s$ laminates.

$$\underline{C}_D^{L(i)} = (\underline{I} - \underline{D}^{L(i)}) \underline{C}^{L(i)} \quad (2)$$

$$\underline{C}_D = \sum_{i=1}^p \left(\underline{C}_D^{L(i)} \right) \quad (3)$$

in which, $\underline{C}^{L(i)}$ and $\underline{C}_D^{L(i)}$ are the stiffness matrix of the undamaged and damaged plies. \underline{C}_D is the stiffness matrix of the damaged laminate. p is the number of plies within the laminate.

The microscopic parameters necessary to define a crack density within samples are related to the unstuck fibre-matrix interfaces and the number of coalescences. It is worth noting that the polished section of specimens do not inform us about the damage within the third direction. In this way, only some surfacic crack densities are measured.

Measurements of crack densities are achieved on $(\pm 45)_s$ laminates and values are plotted in figure 6 versus stresses. It appears that the damage initiation within samples is delayed when the strain rate increases.

Figure 6. Microcrack densities versus stress within $(\pm 45)_s$ laminates.

Such crack density measurements are difficult to achieve and we choose to use a macroscopic damage indicator to quantify the strain rate and temperature effects on the damage initiation and the damage propagation. Since the damage is representative of cracks and hollows within the material, it is responsible of the specimen effective volume decrease. Therefore, from the effective stress concept, it is quite justified to estimate the damage level within each specimen from measurements of its residual properties. The tensile elastic longitudinal modulus E_{xxD} of the damaged samples is chosen as a damage indicator. It is measured by means of a static tensile test applied to the damaged specimens ($V = 0.1$ mm/min) and it is defined as the slope of the stress versus strain curve. The tensile elastic longitudinal modulus of undamaged laminates (E_{xx0}) is used as the reference damage indicator. A macroscopic damage variable D is then defined as :

$$D = \frac{E_{xx0} - E_{xxD}}{E_{xx0}} \quad (4)$$

To valid the use of such a damage indicator, we establish a comparison between the macroscopic damage variable D deduced from the longitudinal modulus measurements and the same damage variable issued from the calculation by using the previous model. Values, related to the $(\pm 45)_s$ laminates, are plotted in figure 7. The good agreement between the two damage variables proves the efficiency of the longitudinal modulus to give information about the damage level of composites submitted to intralaminar cracking.

The evolution law of the damage variable D , versus stress, is of the same shape whatever the laminate. The damage variable is near zero until it reaches the "damage initiation threshold". Beyond, the damage variable linearly increases. Related to the damage initiation and the damage growth within samples, two parameters are defined and measured (Figure 7). The first one is the

stress at the damage initiation while the other is the linear slope of the damage variable D increase ($\partial D/\partial \sigma$). This last parameter is a damage propagation rate indicator.

Figure 7. Microscopic D_1 and macroscopic D_2 damage variable evolutions within $(\pm 45)_S$ laminates ($\dot{\epsilon} = 4.8 \text{ s}^{-1}$).

Figure 8. Damage thresholds and damage propagation rates : (a, b) at room temperature, (c, d) : at -10°C and $+60^\circ\text{C}$.

From figure 8.a, it appears that the damage initiation threshold linearly increases versus the logarithm of strain rate. On the other hand, the damage rate of increase ($\partial D/\partial \sigma$) decreases when the strain rate increases (Figure 8.b). Furthermore, A high level of the transverse stress rate within composites is responsible of a premature damage initiation (Figure 8.a). Then, the damage propagates rapidly (Figure 8.b).

Further tensile tests on $(\pm 45)_S$ laminates are achieved for various temperature conditions. From figures 8.c and 8.d, it appears that the damage initiation and the damage propagation within composites are modified in similar manners with a strain rate increase or a temperature decrease.

MODELLING

At this stage, a new micromechanical calculation based on the stiffness prediction by the MORI and TANAKA approach is proposed to predict, by using a transformation technique from the microscopic scale to the macroscopic one, the macroscopic behaviour of composites [9].

On the basis of the damage kinetics within $(\pm\theta)_s$ laminates, this model consists in defining an undamaged system with the same behaviour than those of the damaged material. Our aim is to use the main results of the ESHELBY and MORI-TANAKA models to compute the elastic mechanical properties of the damaged composites.

In this way, the damage kinetics is explained as the evolution of the number of the debonded fibre-matrix interfaces within samples. This microscopic damage parameter is used because of the employed undamaged-damaged equivalent system. In fact, the volume of fibres with a partially damaged interface is fictitiously replaced by a similar volume constituted with matrix and voids (Figure 10).

Figure 10. Fictive representation of fibres with a partially damaged interface.

The fictive volume of matrix models the strain resistance due to some friction effects at the damaged fibre-matrix interfaces. The fictive volume of voids takes into account the material loss of stiffness when it is submitted to transverse stresses. Therefore, a representative volume which is constituted with matrix, fibres and voids is defined. It is worth noting that the volume of voids is defined as a succession of disc shape elements to be assimilated, like the fibres, to some ellipsoïds (Figure 10). In this way, the hypothesis of the ESHELBY and MORI-TANAKA models are verified. So, the stiffness matrix of an undamaged laminate is explained as a function of the fibre orientation, the initial volume ratios of fibres and matrix while the stiffness matrix of a damaged specimen is deduced from the fibre orientation and the fictive volume ratios of fibres, matrix and void [4].

By applying several macroscopic stress steps to the laminates, it is therefore possible to compute their elastic strain (Figure 11). A good agreement is observed between the computed values and the experiments.

CONCLUSION

The above described impact tensile testing apparatus appear to be reliable for investigating the damage processes within composite materials. When this technique is carried out on $(\pm\theta)_s$ ($45 < \theta < 50$) laminates in which the intralaminar shear stress field within samples is optimum with respect to transverse stresses, the history of the material degradation can be known. In this way, we clearly show that the non-linear behaviour of $(\pm\theta)_s$ E glass fibre reinforced epoxy composites is governed by some fibre-matrix debonding.

A strain rate increase, or a temperature decrease, delays the damage initiation and reduces the damage propagation rate. Furthermore, A high level of the transverse stress rate within composites is responsible of a premature damage initiation. Then, the damage propagates rapidly.

Finally, from the experiments, a micromechanical calculation based on the stiffness prediction by the MORI and TANAKA approach is proposed to predict, by using a translation technique from the microscopic to the macroscopic scales, the macroscopic behaviour of composites.

Figure 11. Experimental and simulated damaged elastic behaviours of some laminates :
 (a) $(\pm 40)_S$ ($\dot{\epsilon} = 3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), (b) $(\pm 45)_S$ ($\dot{\epsilon} = 3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) and (c) $(\pm 50)_S$ ($\dot{\epsilon} = 3 \text{ s}^{-1}$).

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